

The Distinctiveness of the 'Rajdharmā' as Expounded by Shukracharya in the Vedic Political Tradition and Its Relevance in the Contemporary Global Context.

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Abstract

Every discipline in the Indian knowledge tradition has repeatedly demonstrated its timeless importance, universality, and utility across the world. Whether it concerns the suffering humanity, afflicted by threefold miseries—physical, divine, and spiritual—or various concerns such as environmental issues, the rich knowledge tradition of the Indian Vedic scriptures and sages has shown pathways to resolve these problems, proving its relevance. Today, when we observe the global scenario, a web of diverse problems is spread everywhere—disorder, wars, anarchy, terrorism, separatism, illegal immigration, poverty, unemployment, polarization, agricultural issues, climate change, malnutrition, inflation, financial mismanagement, among others. Entangled in these problems, several nations and many cultures have either lost their existence or are struggling for survival. As a result of these various struggles, humanity is facing existential threats, and eventually, it is the human race that is bearing the brunt of these consequences.

If we attempt to trace the root causes of these problems, the subtle and widespread flaws in the governance systems of various nations can be identified as responsible. While modern heads of state govern based on the principles of contemporary political science, they are failing to achieve the great objective of ensuring the welfare and prosperity of the people due to the lack of desired outcomes and the abundance of undesirable situations. With this global problem at the center, the purpose of this research paper is to evaluate the possibilities and limitations of Vedic solutions, testing their utility in today's context. Golden principles of "Ancient Indian Vedic Political Science" can be found in Vedic literature, such as the Samhitas, Brahmanas, Aranyakas, Upanishads, Vedangas, Ramayana, Mahabharata, and independent treatises on political science. Independent texts on political science like Shukraniti, Manusmriti, Kamandakiyanitisara, Nitiprakashika, Rajnitiprakash, Nitimayukh, Barhaspatya Sutra, etc., provide an extensive elaboration on the principles of Vedic political science. Among these, Shukraniti stands out as the most excellent and comprehensive due to its unique subject matter and brilliant exposition of political science principles. In this precious text, Shukraniti, there is an extensive discussion on various subjects such as the origin of the state, the emergence of kingship, the components of a state, Rajdharmā (the duties of kings), the

relationship between the ruler and the people, principles of taxation, foreign policy, environmental conservation, commerce, law, military power, state treasury, budget allocation, public welfare, diplomacy, espionage, the four-fold strategy of Sama, Dana, Bheda, and Danda, the king's character and conduct, etc. In this research paper, along with presenting the principles related to various topics of political science found in Shukraniti, a comparative study and evaluation of the related principles established in other texts that elucidate Vedic political science has also been conducted. By examining the principles of Vedic political science propounded by various sages, golden rules for governance emerge, which, if followed, can help a ruler effectively govern their people. The objective of the proposed research paper is to evaluate the various political science principles found in Shukraniti within the context of 'Vedic Political Science' as established by the Vedic sages. By examining and analyzing the principles of Vedic political science propounded by various sages, golden rules emerge related to governance, which, if followed, can easily help any ruler achieve the highest goals concerning the welfare of the people.

Keywords: Vedanga, Kalpashastra, Dandaniti, Shadgunya, Saptaprakriti, Rajdharmā, Upaaya, Theory of Kingship, Revenue Administration, Principles of Tax Collection, Rajamandala, Addiction.

Introduction:

In the context of Indian political science, if one attempts to determine the origin period of this discipline, the numerous hymns and verses in the Rigveda suggest that political science is as ancient as the Rigveda itself. It is true that the Rigveda and other representative texts of Vedic literature cannot be termed as independent works on political science. However, various principles related to political science are abundantly found throughout the entire Vedic corpus (including the Yajurveda, Samaveda, Atharvaveda, Brahmanas, Aranyakas, Upanishads, and Vedangas). In comparative evaluation, the Atharvaveda is richer than the Rigveda in terms of content related to 'Rajavidya' (the science of governance). Principles related to 'Rajadharma' (the duties of a king) are found in hymns associated with various deities such as Varuna, Indra, and Mitra. Varuna is frequently depicted as a king in the Rigveda: Here is the transliteration of the given text in Roman script: "*Tvam viśveṣām varuṇāsi rājā ye ca devā asura ye ca martāḥ*" (Rigveda; 2.27.10). Apart from hymns and mantras related to Varuna and other Vedic deities, the duties of a king are also elaborated upon in other sections. Among the independent texts on 'Dandaneeti' (the science of punishment), 'Nripaneeti' (the science of kingship), and 'Rajashastra' (the science of governance), 'Shukraneeti' holds a prominent place. Scholars of political science regard 'Shukraneeti' as a pre-Christian text. Compared to texts like Manusmriti, Kamandakiyaneetisara, Yajnavalkyasmriti, Kautilya's Arthashastra, Brihaspatisutra, Rajanitiratnakar,

Neetimayukh, Neetiprakashika, and Rajanitiprakashika, 'Shukraneeti' is notable for covering both common and easily accessible topics related to governance, as well as more subtle and complex issues. The influence of Vedic political science on this timeless work is clearly observable. While the Vedic sages spoke of Varuna as being 'Dhritavrata' (one who maintains vows): Here is the transliteration of the given text in Roman script: "*Niṣasāda dhṛtavrato varuṇaḥ pastyāsvā sāmṛājyā ya sukṛtuḥ*" (Rigveda; 1/25/10), Acharya Shukra also outlines various rules, disciplines, and resolutions for kings in the 'Shukraneeti'. Vedic sages provided ample guidance on subjects such as the king's spies, the king's role as a 'Dandadhara' (bearer of punishment), punishing wrongdoers, protecting the people (*Deva viśvasya bhuvanasya gopā -Rigveda 2.27.4*) and the king's paternal-like behavior towards his subjects ("*Apo niṣiñcann asuraḥ pitā naḥ*" - Atharvaveda 4.15.12). The subsequent scholars of political science, building on the Vedic sages' tradition of knowledge, have enriched the legacy of the 'Nripaneeti' literature.

The Origin and Nature of a King

In the Indian context, when examining theories related to the origin of kings, the doctrine of divine origin for kings is given significant importance. This doctrine strongly supports the view that a king is born from the essence of various supreme deities¹ and, according to the time, place, and circumstances, the king acts in a manner akin to these deities, performing specific tasks thoughtfully. Even Vedic literature provides ample support for this divine origin of kings. In these texts, the Vedic deity Varuna is often established as a steadfast king '*Dhṛtavrata*'². Following this tradition, the 'Shukraneeti' states that a king becomes the ruler of the material world by constantly upholding the essence of deities such as Indra, Vayu, Yama, Surya, Agni, Varuna, Chandra, and Kubera³. This means that a king embodies the attributes of Indra in protection and taxation, Vayu in inspiring good and bad deeds, Surya in destroying the darkness of adharma, Yama in punishing wrongdoers, Agni in purity and reception of offerings, Varuna in nourishing all through wealth, Chandra in delighting his subjects, and Kubera in safeguarding the state's treasures. Among these, Acharya Shukra considers the quality of delight, represented by Chandra, as the most important virtue for a king. In the Yajurveda⁴, the term '*Divah Sūnuh*' (son of the heavens) is used to indicate that the king is a descendant of the gods.

The Septenary and Composite Form of the State

Although terms such as *Rāṣṭra*⁵, Amatya (minister), King, Army, Treasury, Friend, and Fort appear in multiple instances in the Rigveda, they do not clearly denote the components of the state. However, in the Yajurveda, the state is conceptualized as a Cosmic Being (Virat Purusha) and is described with components like Nation, Wealth, Fame, Energy, Strength, Effort, Kshatriya Duty, Allied Forces, Knowledge, and Justice⁶. Subsequent scholars, building upon this

Vedic description of the state, firmly established the concept of a 'Saptanga' (seven-limbed) state: 'Swaamyam Aatyaashcha Rashtrañcha Durgañ Kosho Balñ Suhrid'⁷. In this context, the 'Shukraneeti' elaborates the concept of the state as a tree, with the king as the root, the ministers as the trunk, the generals as the branches, the army as the leaves, the people as the flowers, the land as the fruits, and the state's territory as the seeds⁸.

General Duties of the King

The Mahabharata's Shantiparva is widely accepted by scholars of political science as an encyclopedic text on Vedic political science and duties of kings. Scholars have recognized and presented the principles outlined in the Shantiparva of the Mahabharata in their works. A well-known saying related to royal duties is: '*lokarañjanamevātra rājñām dharmah sanātanaḥ*'⁹ which means that the primary duty of a king is to keep his subjects happy and content. In texts such as 'Shukraneeti', 'Shukraneetisara', and 'Kamandakiyaneetisara', the duties of the king are extensively elaborated. The king is instructed never to cause distress to his subjects for any personal gain. A wise king should never cause his people suffering, even if he himself faces hardship. He should avoid adopting any form of livelihood or conduct that is harmful. "Even if one becomes as motionless as a pillar due to suffering from hunger, one should not adopt a livelihood or practice that is filled with misfortune."¹⁰ The king must always pay heed to the advice of his ministers regarding what is beneficial or detrimental. A king who does not adhere to these principles should be considered a 'dasyu' (robber) who merely exploits the wealth of the subjects. The king should be delightful like the autumn moon to scholars, intolerable like the summer sun to enemies, and neither too soft nor too harsh to the people¹¹. The king should show softness only towards Brahmins. According to Acharya Shukra, if the king shows softness towards people other than Brahmins, those of lower status might behave like elephant drivers¹², disrespecting the king as they would an elephant. The king should always issue written orders and never give any command, large or small, without written documentation: "*nṛpasamcīnhitam lekhyam nṛpatastanna nṛpo nṛpaḥ*" only a command stamped with the royal seal is considered valid. A king should remain vigilant in his duties, as his awareness ensures that his assistants are also diligent. Conversely, if a king is negligent, his assistants will also exhibit negligence in their responsibilities.

The Fourfold Strategy of Sama, Dana, Bheda, and Danda

It is the king's duty to ensure that through the use of the fourfold strategies¹³—Sama (conciliation), Dana (gifts), Bheda (division), and Danda (punishment)—he does not allow his friends, enemies, or indifferent neighboring kings to become too powerful. For enemies, the strategies should be applied in the following order: first, Sama; then, Dana; followed by Bheda. Only when these three strategies fail and life is in danger should Danda be used. A king who is brave, industrious for progress, and equipped with strength and strategy, will find

that other kings, while outwardly appearing friendly, will secretly harbor animosity and wait for the right moment to strike. Therefore, it is advantageous for a king to remain vigilant from this perspective. According to Maharishi Shukra, a king should strive to strengthen weaker kings and weaken stronger allies. For hostile kings, he should create division through Sama and Bheda and attempt to weaken, distress, and destroy them¹⁴. Shukra deems it best to use Sama and Dana for extremely powerful enemies, Sama and Bheda for enemies stronger than the king, Bheda and Danda for equally matched kings, and only Danda for weaker enemies. For friendly kings, only Sama and Dana should be used, and a king should never employ Bheda or Danda against his allies. Efforts should always be made to gather those who are distressed by enemies through Sama and Dana.

Ideal Governance of the Subjects

According to Vedic political philosophy, the existence of a state fundamentally relies on its subjects¹⁵. Thus, it is the king's duty to govern his subjects using only Sama and Dana. The use of Bheda and Danda on one's own subjects is prohibited: "*svaprajānām na bhedenā naiva daṇḍena pālanam.*" Acharya Shukra asserts that the king should become a upholder of dharma by using Danda for righteousness. Defining Danda, Shukra states: "*nivṛttirasadācārāddamanam daṇḍataśca tatyena saṁdamyate janturūpāyo daṇḍa eva saḥ.*" This means that Danda is the means to eliminate improper conduct and behavior, and it refers to any method that effectively achieves such control. By employing policies including Danda, a king's actions are accomplished effectively. Acharya Shukra considers the king to be a catalyst of the age, asserting: "*yugapravarttako rājā dharmādharmaḥpraśikṣaṇāt.*" The dharma or adharma of the ages, such as the Satya Yuga, does not depend on the age or the subjects but rather on whether the king is righteous or unrighteous. A righteous king will lead his subjects towards dharma, while a sinful king will lead his subjects towards adharma. The king should renounce lust and anger. Acharya Shukra regards only the king who renounces desire, anger, and greed, and upholds Danda, as truly virtuous. Clearly, traits like being effeminate, angry, and greedy are considered flaws in a king. A king's duty is to first purify himself, then ensure the purity of his attendants, and finally work towards the purification of his subjects. The king who observes and rectifies his own and his subjects' faults is considered superior. Shukra has clarified that a king can achieve the ideal state of governance by embodying the qualities of father, mother, teacher, brother, kinsman, Kubera, and Yama. The Agni Purana¹⁶ emphasizes that just as a pregnant woman forsakes her own comfort for the care of her unborn child, a king should also forget his own comfort and always focus on the welfare and satisfaction of his subjects.

Supervision and Compliance of the Royal Staff's Duties and Conduct

According to Maharishi Manu, even ordinary tasks become difficult when performed by a single individual. Therefore, managing the state, a much more complex duty, cannot be carried out by the king alone. In the Vedic tradition of political science, the king himself is considered a servant who receives a sixth portion from the people, which means it is his duty to protect them.¹⁷ Consequently, the principles of political science have established rules regarding the duties, compliance, and supervision of royal employees who assist in state affairs. According to Acharya Shukra, a king should appoint servants based on their capability to sustain their dependents with their salary. As a servant becomes more capable and qualified, the king should diligently increase their salary for his own benefit. Providing minimal wages can turn such servants into enemies, as they may be forced to seek other means of sustenance, potentially turning against the king, robbing him, and exploiting the people.¹⁸ The king should either keep a sixth or a fourth portion of the servant's salary and return half or the entire amount after two or three years. Additionally, the king should provide an eighth part of the salary as a reward annually and more promptly to those who work harder. For servants who have served the king for over forty years, the king should establish a lifelong pension of half the salary and continue to provide half the salary to the servant's children until they are of working age. Similarly, the king should give one-fourth of the salary to the servant's virtuous wife and unmarried daughter.¹⁹ If a servant dies while serving the master, it is the king's duty to ensure that the deceased servant's salary continues to be provided to their son until he grows up and is capable of working. Acharya Shukra asserts that a king who uses harsh language with his servants, fails to provide full salaries, imposes severe punishments, or insults them, essentially teaches his servants to be hostile. It is also the king's duty to encourage his subjects to take care of their families. Acharya Shukra has prescribed that a royal servant who does not properly care for their parents, spouse, or other dependents, and engages in improper behavior, should be imprisoned and employed in public works such as road construction or repairs, with half of their salary given to their family²⁰. The rules concerning the maintenance of state employees as outlined by Acharya Shukra align with the duties of the king as prescribed in the Yajurveda²¹, which state that the king is appointed for the welfare, maintenance, prosperity, and security of the people. The Brahman texts also include oaths taken during the king's coronation, which emphasize the responsibility of ensuring the well-being of the subjects²².

Governance by Law

An examination of the principles of Vedic political science reveals that the emergence of kingship and political science was intended to free societies from anarchy²³, immorality, fear, war²⁴, and enemies, and to establish the rule of law and dharma. Without a king, anarchy prevails, and the powerful oppress the weak in the same manner that large fish devour smaller ones in the ocean. The Puranas²⁵ and texts like the Manusmriti clearly state that Brahma created kings from parts

of various deities to ensure justice and the protection of all creation. Therefore, it is the king's duty to neither protect nor allow those engaged in adharmas such as friends, sons, teachers, thieves, or aggressors to remain in his kingdom.²⁶ Maharishi Shukra describes aggressors as those who use fire, poison, or weapons to harm, steal wealth, and seize fields and women. The king should never place complete trust in any person, including sons, brothers, wives, ministers, or officials, due to the pervasive greed for wealth, women, and power. Like a constant flame, the king must remain vigilant and always be ready to destroy the wicked and address both internal and external threats to the state.

Management of the Treasury, Taxation, and Financial Systems

Acharya Shukra has prescribed that a king must protect his treasury in any way necessary to safeguard his state, army, and sacrificial rites. The treasury accumulated by the king for these purposes benefits both the king and the subjects in this world and the next. In contrast, Treasures amassed solely for one's own enjoyment or for one's wife and children are to be known as leading only to hell-*'strīputrārtham kṛto yaśca svopabhogāya kevalam narakāyaiva sa jñeyo na paratra sukhapradahī'*²⁷. The king should seize wealth from an unjust ruler and adopt similar measures with an enemy king. The king must not impose taxes on pilgrimage sites, temples, or their assets without a significant reason: "*anāpadi na kurvīta tīrthadevakaragrahāt*". If a king accumulates wealth through injustice, abandoning righteous paths, or by causing suffering to his people, this wealth quickly falls under enemy control. However, if a king is dedicated to the destruction of his enemies and is engaged in expanding and empowering his army for this purpose, he may impose higher taxes or penalties on his subjects to accumulate wealth: "*yadā śatruvināśārtham balasamrakṣaṇodyataḥ viśiṣṭadaṇḍaśulkādi dhanam lokāttadā haretī*." Acharya Shukra believes that a king should maintain a treasury sufficient to sustain his army for twenty years without relying on penalties or taxes. The significance of the treasury is highlighted in Shukraniti, stating that the treasury is the primary source of strength, meaning the army's wealth is accumulated through it, and the army's protection is facilitated by the treasury. Thus, protecting the treasury and the army leads to the growth of the treasury and the state while destroying enemies. These goals can only be achieved through the single means of protecting the people: "*tattrayaṁ svargaḥ prajāsamrakṣaṇena vai*."²⁸ By protecting the people, the king ensures the growth of the treasury and the state, the destruction of enemies, and ultimately, his own ascension to heaven. The king should adopt the mindset of a gardener, who nurtures and protects the trees of a garden with care and attention, just as a king should cultivate his subjects and manage them to yield taxes. A king who follows this principle is considered superior. A king who increases the treasury through trade or business is regarded as intermediate, while a king who relies on services, penalties, pilgrimage sites, and temples for increasing the treasury is considered inferior: "*adhamah sevyā daṇḍatīrthadevakaragrahāḥ*". A

king should never forcibly acquire property from subjects without paying its value. Such reprehensible actions can lead to the destruction of the king's lineage by igniting a fiery rebellion among the subjects: "*anyathā svaprajātāpo nṛpaṁ dahati sānvayam*." Acharya Shukra advises that a king should accumulate enough grain for three years to ensure the state's welfare and protection. He should handle wealth prudently like a miser and, when the time is right, relinquish it like a renunciant. The king should collect taxes only once on all goods and avoid deceptive, repeated taxation on the same item within his state: "*kvacinnāivāsakṛcchulke rāṣṭre grāhyaṁ nṛpaiśchalāt*". Regarding taxation, Shukraniti provides universal and timeless guidance for kings, suggesting that a king should act like a gardener rather than a charcoal maker. Just as a gardener uses fertilizers and water to nurture and selects only the ripe fruits, blossoms, and mature roots, a king should prioritize the welfare of his people while collecting minimal and just taxes. In contrast, a charcoal maker destroys the entire tree to obtain its root, similar to how an imprudent king's careless taxation can lead to the destruction of both his subjects and himself. Regarding taxes on farmers, Acharya Shukra states that the king should levy only as much tax as will not lead to their ruin. If a farmer pays a tax equivalent to one hundred silver coins, the king should return five percent of this tax as a reward to encourage the farmer. Generally, where the tax on items like milk and grains is a sixteenth, provisions for family maintenance, such as milk from kept cows and purchased clothing, should be exempt from taxes. The king should periodically inspect the tools used by those engaged in metalworking and similar trades to ensure their proper use.

Allocation of State Revenue and Expenditure

The usage of state revenue from various sources and the proportion of expenditure are addressed differently in the texts of political science. In the "Shivatattvaratnakara,"²⁹ Kelaadi Basavabhoopaal, proposes that the king should divide the state revenue into four parts: one part to be saved in the permanent treasury and the remaining three parts to be used for the fulfillment of the threefold objectives of Dharma (duty), Artha (prosperity), and Kama (desires). In contrast, Acharya Shukra's view on the allocation and utilization of state revenue is that the king should divide the entire revenue into six parts.

Of these, three parts should be allocated for military expenses. Half of the remaining portion, or one-twelfth of the total revenue, should be used for donations. Another half should be allocated for officials' salaries, another half for personal enjoyment, and one-sixth of the total revenue should be reserved in the permanent treasury. It is the king's primary duty to carefully manage and protect the acquired wealth, grow it following righteous paths, and invest it wisely in deserving causes³⁰.

Regulation of Taverns

From the inception of the state and kingship, efforts were made to keep both the state and the king free from the vices of alcohol. A state or king successful in maintaining abstinence from alcohol considered this a significant achievement. The Upanishads also contain instances where liberation from alcohol is considered an accomplishment. For example, King Ashwapati declares that in his realm, there is neither avarice nor consumption of alcohol³¹. The Vedic tradition of kingship acknowledges alcohol, its consumption, and taverns as sources of crime and immorality: '*mṛgayāksāstathā pānam garhitāni mahībhujām*'. Acharya Shukra states that the king should ensure that taverns are located outside the village and that drinkers remain there, with a prohibition on drinking during the day: "*na divā madyapānam hi rāṣṭre kuryādi karhicit*".³²

Environmental Protection

Acharya Shukra defines the nation as encompassing both stationary (such as rivers, trees, and mountains) and mobile entities (like cattle and humans)- '*sthāvaram jaṅgam vāpi rāṣṭraśabdena gīyate*'³³. Therefore, it is the king's duty to protect the nation with utmost effort³⁴. The Yajurveda's prayer to the Earth emphasizes this: O Earth, my mother, do not harm me, nor do I cause you harm- '*pr̥thivi mātarmā mā hiṁsīh, mo aham tvām*'. This indicates that the king should focus on the protection and prosperity of trees, the environment, and vegetation. In terms of tree planting and maintenance, Acharya Shukra advises that trees in villages should be planted in the village, and those in forests should be planted in the forest. The king should also attend to irrigation, fertilization, and the development of fruit and flowers on these trees³⁵. Additionally, the king should construct and protect water bodies such as wells, reservoirs, ponds, and lakes throughout the state, ensuring that these water bodies have steps built around them for access. Tree planting is considered a means of achieving the fourfold objectives of Dharma, Artha, Kama, and Moksha³⁶.

Public Welfare and Enjoyment

The Atharvaveda underscores that the king should always be vigilant about the state and the people's welfare: '*viśi rāṣṭre jāgr̥hi rohitasya*'. Ancient political science scholars describe the king as the body of the people and the people as the body of the king. Clearly, the king and the people are interrelated; the happiness of the people results in the king's happiness, and the king's welfare is reflected in the state's provision of benefits and comforts to the people. According to Acharya Narada³⁷, Brahma made the king a servant of the people; thus, pleasing the people

is the king's primary duty. The king should establish temples to deities like Vishnu, Shiva, Ganesha, the Sun, or other gods suitable for the local community in villages: "*śrīṅgātake grāmamadhye viṣṇorvā śaṁkarasya ca | gaṇeśasya raverdevyāḥ prāsādān kramato nyaset*". Acharya Shukra has praised the construction of deity images as beneficial, while creating images of humans is deemed inauspicious and obstructive to attaining heavenly realms: "*devānām pratibimbāni kuryācchreyaskarāni ca | svargyāni mānavādīnāmasvargyānyaśubhāni ca*". The king should also organize festivals for these deities: "*evaṁvidhān nṛpo rāṣṭre devān saṁsthāpayet sadā pratisaṁvatsare teṣāmutsavān samyagācare*".³⁸ It is also the king's duty to restore any dilapidated or worn-out temples and images. The king should protect festivals organized by the people and ensure their joy. The king should be delighted by the people's happiness and distressed by their sorrow- "*prajānandena saṁtuṣyet tadduḥkhairduḥkhito bhavet*".

Penal Code

In Vedic political science, the king's duties are clearly defined: to embody the valor of Indra, to make enemies weep, and to destroy proud sinners. In the Krita Yuga, King Prithu, who first established the state, pledged before the sages to rule according to the principles of justice, and it was upon this pledge that he was made king³⁹. According to Acharya Shukra, if a dispute arises among the subjects, it is the king's duty to carefully consider the matter and punish the enemies and wrongdoers. A king who acts in this manner will ensure that his subjects remain loyal and always adhere to his commands. The king must examine legal proceedings and judgments with great care, in the presence of learned advisors, ministers, Brahmins, and priests⁴⁰. It is not permissible for the king or the members of the judicial council to view or hear cases in isolation or privately. A king who, out of ignorance, indulges in pleasures and neglects judicial duties, or who makes decisions without consulting the litigants and council members, will face the destruction of his subjects, the growth of enemies, the loss of his own life, and the torments akin to hell. Therefore, Shukra clearly advises that the king should always conduct proceedings according to the scriptures: "*tasmācchāstrānusāreṇa rājā kāryāni sādhayet*". The king should avoid using capital punishment. Instead of killing, he should apply other severe punishments, as the scriptures advocate against the killing of living beings: "*na nihanyācca bhūtānitviti jāgarti vai śrutih*". If an enemy king, nation, or minister conspires to harm, the king should order their elimination. If a group or faction becomes anti-national, the king should not attempt to destroy them all at once but should address each group individually.⁴¹

Appointment of State Officials

Maharshi Vaishampayana has stated that the king can appoint two or three judges to help execute judicial functions for the benefit of the people⁴². If the king is unable to personally oversee legal matters, he should appoint a Brahmin who

is well-versed in the Vedas, self-controlled, noble, impartial, calm, free from restlessness, faithful in both this world and the next, fearful of the afterlife, religious, industrious, and free from anger (a well-educated and wise individual). If such a Brahmin is not available, the king may appoint a Kshatriya (a person skilled in administration and knowledgeable in dharma) or a Vaishya for judicial duties, but under no circumstances should a Shudra (an uneducated person) be appointed as a representative in judicial matters⁴³. The king should also be cautious in appointing members to the advisory council, selecting those who are knowledgeable, wise, virtuous, of good character, free from partiality, dharmaconscious, truthful, industrious, and who have conquered desire, anger, and greed.

Judicial Principles and Decision-Making

In Vedic jurisprudence, Varuna is acknowledged as the primary judge⁴⁴, whose system of punishment ensures that no criminal escapes justice. Shukra's teachings state that if proper decisions are not made by the appropriate classes, the matter should be decided by the guilds, and if unresolved by them, by the councils, and if still undecided, by the officers appointed by the king: "*vicārya śreṇibhiḥ kāryam kulairyanna vicāritam gaṇaiśca śreṇyavijñātam gaṇājñātam niyuktakaiḥ*". Among the various classes, the king's recognition in matters of dharma and adharma (righteousness and unrighteousness) holds the highest authority. For judicial decisions, the king should rely on ten resources⁴⁵: the king himself, the officers, the elders, memory, astrologers, writers, gold, fire, water, and men. It is the king's eternal duty to uphold the traditional dharma of the country, caste, guild, and family. Altering these traditions without cause creates unrest among the people: "*tathaiva te pālaniyāḥ prajā prakṣubhyate'nyathā*". It has often been observed that ministers or judges sometimes give biased decisions contrary to rules. In such cases, it is the king's duty to impose a heavy monetary penalty on such officials. This is because without punishment, no one can remain on the right path: "*nahi jātu vinā daṇḍam kaścinmārgē'vatiṣṭhate*"⁴⁶. Shukra's teachings also identify five causes of bias: attachment, greed, fear, enmity, and hearing litigants' statements in private.

Commercial Regulations

In ancient Vedic political science, commercial regulation is classified into three types of duties: external, internal, and hospitality. These are further divided into two categories: permissible and entry-related⁴⁷. The king is responsible for overseeing trade regulations. He should ensure that merchants only take a sixteenth or thirty-second part of the cost price as profit: "*dvātrimśāṁsam ṣoḍaśāṁsam lābham paṇye niyojayet*"⁴⁸. The king is also responsible for protecting the subjects from moneylenders who exploit them through compound interest. If a moneylender collects more than double the principal amount, the king should ensure that the debtor only repays the original principal. A person selling defective goods deceitfully is subject to punishment by the king: - "*kūṭapanyasya vikretā sa daṇḍayaścauravat sadā*". A person who sells metals like gold with adulteration beyond the regulated quantity should be penalized

with a fine double the value of the metal: *'dhātūnām kūṭakārī tu dviguṇo daṇḍamarhati'*. Various dharmasūtras⁴⁹ provide detailed rules on the rates of taxes on goods.

Fortification

The Vedic penal code includes a discussion of various types of fortifications. In the Shantiparva of the Mahabharata⁵⁰, fortifications are categorized as follows: Maru (desert fort), Mahidurg (land fort), Giridurg (mountain fort), Nridurg (human-built fort), Jaladurg (water fort), and Vanadurg (forest fort). Among the seven elements of the state, fortification (durg) is considered vital. According to Shukra Niti⁵¹, the fortifications are classified in the following order of superiority: Parikh (fortified city), Airin (fortified structure), Paridh (boundary fort), Van (forest fort), Dhanv (armored fort), Jal (water fort), and Giridurg (mountain fort). Of these, the "military fort" is regarded as the best: *'śreṣṭham tu sarvadurgebhyaḥ senādurgam smṛtam budhaiḥ'*. Thus, the king should ensure that his forts are well-equipped with provisions, brave soldiers, weapons, and resources. He should always reside in such well-prepared forts.

Military or Force

The Vedas describe the existence of large armies in various passages. The Yajurveda mentions that Indra commanded a hundred armies: *'śatām senā ajayat sākamindraḥ'*. The Atharvaveda⁵² advises the king to attack with his army and achieve victory over enemies. In political science, 'force' is recognized as a crucial factor. Shukra Niti emphasizes that defeating even ordinary enemies becomes difficult without sufficient force. Therefore, gods, demons, and humans all employ military means to overcome adversaries when lacking in strength. Acharya Shukra identifies six types of forces: physical strength, bravery, military strength, armament strength, intellectual strength, and longevity. Although human strength is essential for defeating enemies, the king should adopt formidable strength to subdue opponents. Shukra Niti prescribes that the king's army should be organized as follows:

for every cavalryman, there should be four times as many infantrymen; for each cavalryman, there should be one-fifth as many oxen, one-eighth as many camels, one-fourth as many elephants, one-half as many chariots, and twice as many large artillery pieces (like cannons)⁵³. The king should station a unit of soldiers every

hundred yojanas within the realm: *'śatam śatam yojanānte sainyam rāṣṭre niyojayet'*. The king should not lead a small force against minor enemies but should deploy a newly recruited large army for attacks. The king should avoid actions that might cause discord within the army. Shukraniti elaborates on this and notes that harsh words, severe punishments, low wages, excessive fear, constant travel, and overwork can create divisions in the army. Therefore, the king should avoid such practices.

Rules and Legality of Warfare

The king should consider the time, place, enemy strength, his own strength, and strategies (conciliation, negotiation, division, punishment), as well as *'śāḍgunya'* the six virtues⁵⁴ (alliances, hostilities, transport, location, double dealing, and refuge) and counsel before initiating war. Upon the onset of war, the general should first engage the enemy with half of the army. Subsequently, there should be a battle between the armies under the ministers, followed by a battle between the king's forces and the enemy king's forces. In extreme cases, where there is a threat to life, the king himself may engage in battle, as sanctioned by the scriptures. Ancient political texts provide detailed conduct codes for warfare, such as: elephants should fight elephants, cavalry should fight cavalry, chariots should fight chariots, infantry should fight infantry, armed soldiers should fight armed soldiers, and those with weapons should fight those with weapons. It is prohibited to attack eunuchs, those with their hands clasped, disheveled, asleep, naked, unarmed, eating, terrified, or those fleeing from battle. Shukraniti specifies that these rules apply to righteous warfare, not to deceptive warfare: *"dharmayuddhe tu kūṭe vai na santi niyamā amī"*. However, 'deceptive warfare' is deemed superior for the destruction of powerful enemies: *'na yuddham kūṭasadrśam nāśanam balavadripoḥ'*.

The King's Virtue and Personal Conduct

In Vedic thought, it is established that 'dharma' is also the protector of rulers, meaning that it controls and governs the ruler⁵⁵. According to Shukraniti, a king who diligently adheres to the rules set by the scriptures is revered by all. A king who diligently performs his duties, embraces good practices, and discards bad ones enjoys long-term prosperity. Conversely, a king who is irregular in his duties, virtue, and promises quickly loses his position, friends, and royal status⁵⁶. A king endowed with righteousness and strength must punish unrighteous kings as thieves. The king's righteousness is crucial, according to Shukra Niti, because the righteousness and unrighteousness of the people *'viś'*⁵⁷ are considered to stem from the king. Thus, a righteous king leads his subjects to righteousness, while an unrighteous king causes his subjects to become unrighteous: *'dharmādharmapravṛttau tu nṛpa eva hi kāraṇam'*. Kings who fail to uphold dharma due to cowardice or greed are considered unfortunate and destined for hell. Even if an enemy king repeatedly gives assurances, the king should not place trust in him and should avoid going alone or with only a few aides to the enemy's

territory. The king should not harbor animosity towards loyal ministers nor act based on the advice of newly appointed individuals, but should rely on the counsel of seasoned ministers. If a new officer is capable and skilled in ethics, he should be treated like experienced officers and eventually appointed alongside them in royal duties. The king should diligently uphold dharma and also compel his subjects to follow the path of righteousness, as a king who follows dharma is followed by a devoted populace. Establishing dharma is essential for a king, as prosperity and fame are achieved through its establishment: *'dharmasamsthāpanādrājā śriyam kīrtim pravindati'*. It is the king's duty to punish those who act against the prescribed dharma of their varna, ashrama, and caste: *"vartayantyanyathā daṇḍayā yā varṇāśramajātayah"*. In times of distress, the king should humbly call and honor scholars, teachers, brothers, relatives, servants, and members of the assembly in the royal court before presenting his requests. The king should avoid starting multiple projects simultaneously and should not begin a new task without completing the ongoing ones: *"nārambhitasamāptim tu vinā cānyam samācari"*. The king must ensure that distinguished individuals receive appropriate respect, and those of lower status do not receive excessive respect; respect should be commensurate. If any person's wealth is stolen by thieves, it is the king's duty to compensate the victim with an equivalent amount from the treasury⁵⁸.

Code of Conduct for State Officials and Subjects

According to Acharya Shukra, the king should ensure that the officials appointed by him reside on lands outside the village. Soldiers should not enter the village without any official duty, nor should they cause distress to the villagers or engage in any interaction with them. The king must ensure that soldiers are not assigned any tasks other than military duties: *"yuddhakriyām vinā sainyaṃ yojyennānyakarmani"*. If a wealthy merchant or farmer falls into hardship due to business transactions, it is the king's duty to assist them and relieve their suffering. The king should protect the wealth of soldiers as his own and, if a soldier is away from the capital, provide the soldier with a sum equivalent to one-third more than the amount spent. If a soldier accumulates wealth through deceitful or unethical means, the king should confiscate all of that wealth⁵⁹: *"samhareddhanikāt sarvaṃ mithyācāraddhanaṃ nṛpaḥ"*. If a moneylender has taken four times the principal amount in interest, the king should ensure that the lender does not collect more than this and should cancel the loan. In terms of punitive measures, the king should strive to avoid administering the death penalty⁶⁰: *"na nihanyācca bhūtāni tviti jāgarti vai śrutihī" tasmāt sarvaprayatnena vadhadāṇaṃ tyajennṛpaḥ"*.

The Duty of Subjects Towards an Unrighteous King

It is the duty of the subjects to encourage an unrighteous king towards righteous conduct. Acharya Shukra asserts that the righteous conduct of the king and his dealings with the subjects are the fundamental basis for the existence of the state. An unrighteous king not only brings about his own downfall but also

the destruction of his subjects and his state. Even if a king is born into a noble lineage, if he is malicious towards virtue, policy, and the army, and is unrighteous, he should be considered a destroyer of the state and should be removed from his position⁶¹. In such cases, it is the duty of the priests to appoint another person from the royal lineage, endowed with royal virtues, with the consent of ministers and advisors, to protect the state⁶². This shows that despite supporting the divine theory of a king's origin in Vedic political philosophy, Acharya Shukra does not support the acceptance of an unrighteous king.

Conclusion

Although the principles of the ancient Indian discipline of 'Political Science' are found in Vedic literature, a detailed and systematic form of Vedic political science is available in independent texts on political science. In the long tradition of political philosophy or Rajavidya, Acharya Shukra and his works are considered most significant due to their depth, uniqueness, completeness, and presentation. In ancient times, when governance was generally operated and controlled by kings, political science texts were created keeping this context in mind. However, the scholars of Rajavidya never ignored Vedic values. The texts authored by Acharya Shukra and other scholars center around the well-being of the subjects. The true 'kingship' of a ruler indeed depends on the satisfaction of the subjects. Although a king is considered a divine element, all his actions and conduct are focused on satisfying the subjects. The king is presented as a servant of the people, and the taxes or shares collected from the subjects are viewed as the king's salary. According to Vedic tradition, the only fundamental duty of a king who receives remuneration in the form of taxes or shares is to protect and please the subjects. In presenting the duties or Rajdharma of a king, Acharya Shukra ensures that no subject suffers, strong individuals do not oppress the weak, traitors and enemy kings are duly punished, exploitation of subjects through interest is prevented, excessive and unjust taxation is avoided, minimal taxation on farmers is enforced, no taxation on teachers (Brahmins) is imposed, causes of rebellion within the military are eradicated, justice is maintained, and wise decisions are made. The king should also keep a close watch on the behavior of neighboring states. The king should conduct himself in such a manner that he inspires his subjects to follow righteous conduct. The duties of kings as outlined in ancient texts are also exemplary for modern heads of state. The lapses in duties prescribed in Vedic political science by leaders of various nations lead to wars, environmental crises, political tensions, violence, regime changes, civil wars, disintegration of nations, revolts, and economic crises. Therefore, it is essential to establish global study and teaching systems for Vedic political science so that universities and study centers worldwide can enlighten the world with the knowledge contained in this discipline of Indian tradition. This would help address contemporary political problems on a global scale.

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